

**A Review of the Evaluation of Quarrying Impacts on Nigeria's Biophysical Ecosystem:
Corporate Social Responsibility and the Missing Link**

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Abstract

Nigeria is one of the most naturally endowed African countries in terms of mineral deposits. Different minerals of various qualities, formed over millions of years, can be found with respect to their associated bedrock geology. Quarrying is the process of extracting these minerals from their sources. Indisputably, the formation rate of minerals is infinitesimal in comparison to the rate of human exploitation, which generally results in deformation of the ecosystem. This study examines the impact of quarrying on Nigeria's biophysical environment. It concludes that there is no stage of quarrying activity without adverse effects on the host communities, that there is absence of genuine Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) implementation on the part of mining industries in Nigeria, and the fact that implemented CSRs are not commensurate to the damage meted on the biophysical environment.

The study recommends incorporation of environmental management principles into the EIA programme such as enforcement of land reclamation; introduction of polluters-pay-principle (PPP); extension of CSRs to host mining communities beyond social amenities; and environmental monitoring section of the EIA to be proactive for environmental restoration.

Key words: biophysical, corporate, environment, quarrying, social, responsibility

Introduction

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) is pertinent to evaluating Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) implementation in mining host communities. Its impact in ameliorating conflicts between the communities and mining organization cannot be overemphasized. Across the globe today, the growth and development of most urbanized mining cities, which were once rural, can be traced to the influence of CSR. It takes different forms based on the agreed deed between the two parties as stated in the initial Environmental Social Impact Assessment (ESIA). However, observations show decline in CSR in developing countries, as well as strategic restriction to provision of basic social infrastructure to host communities while relegating the restoration of the environment. In essence, sole concentration has been on social wellbeing to the neglect of reformation and reclamation of the exploited biophysical

environment. It is worthy of note that often times the amenities provided within and around the mining community may not actually be for the community's benefit but primarily for the benefit of mining companies' staff, especially expatriates. Majority of the environmental-friendly strategies for restoring the deteriorated biosphere are neglected by the companies. Apart from waste management, biotechnological concepts like re-forestation, land reclamation, and bioremediation have no place in the CSR of most mining companies due to cost implications and limited technical know-how. Yet, regardless of the amount of infrastructure provided that may attract community attention, such benevolent acts are incapable of restoring the damaged biosphere. Provision of potable water cannot reduce the atmospheric temperature increased, recharge groundwater depleted, or replenish soil organic content loss, resulting from deforestation and

industrialization. Electricity cannot reduce the ultraviolet radiation and ozone layer depletion caused by greenhouse gases intermittently released into the atmosphere. Clearly, social amenities are unable to reverse the damage done to the ecosystem as a result of mining operations. The irreversible consequences of mining in the biophysical environment range from environmental (surface and ground water contamination, atmospheric pollution, noise pollution, biodiversity loss, etc.) to socio-economic (loss of community livelihood, health challenges, reduction in agricultural productivity, etc.) and others. In Nigeria, the role of mining in severe ecosystem modification at levels beyond recovery is highly pronounced; changing ecosystem patterns from terrestrial to aquatic and vice-versa, especially where open cast mining method predominates.

Common Biophysical Degradation in Mining Industries

Quarrying is an open cast excavation from which fairly massive and deep deposits of hard or soft rocks are extracted, usually for the production of aggregates and stones (Coppin, 1982). It is usually done by open-cast method, using rock drills, explosion of dynamite and other methods. Stripping is the initial step in the quarrying operation and involves removal of the topsoil and sub-soil that covers mineable materials. A variety of equipment is used to strip, transport and redeposit sub-soil (Bauer, 1991). There is a wide range of potential environmental effects caused by quarries which inevitably create negative externalities. The effects of different industrial sectors' activities on the environment are enormous (Odunze and Maduiké, 2018), but it is an incontrovertible statement that damage is being done to the environment worldwide. A report by the World Bank working group on environment sustainability reveals that occupations such as lumbering, mining, quarrying, and sandblasting degrade the

environment and worsen the plight of the poor. Omosanya and Ajibade (2011) also maintain that quarrying negatively affects the environment in a variety of ways during exploration, blasting, transportation and disposal of waste rocks. Major environmental effects are destruction of vegetation; disruption of animal habitats; diversion and blockage of natural drainage systems; soil erosion and river siltation; noise and vibration; and dust pollution. Furthermore, quarries may also damage or destroy sites of scientific, archaeological, and cultural interest, and can negatively affect the local tourism industry. These adverse impacts created by quarrying vary in their frequency and longevity, from occasional short-term low levels of nuisance to daily ever-present disruptions, bearing cumulative or long-term effects and instances of irreparable damage. The scale of these externalities also varies by aggregate type, with dust, blasting and traffic impacts generally being greater at hard rock quarries (DETR, 1998). In 2007, Garg *et al.* (2007) identified some environmental impacts of mining such as water and air pollution, despoliation of land, noise and ground vibration, and accidental and health hazards. Ultimately, quarrying impacts the atmospheric, lithospheric, hydrospheric and biospheric environments.

Lithospheric Impacts of Quarrying

Surface mining disrupts the landscape, as the topsoil and overburden are moved to access the minerals. Open cast (surface) mining removes the top soil and results in deep and large excavation pits and cuts. As such, large areas become unusable and denuded of vegetation, causing continuous soil erosion and resultant effects like silting and degradation of streams and water bodies. Prominent amongst the influence of quarrying is land use change and land degradation. Land use refers to humans' uses of land, or immediate actions modifying or converting

land cover. On the other hand, land cover refers to the natural cover that characterizes a particular area (De Sherbinin, 2002). In this regard, quarrying is one of the land use types aimed at extraction of non-fuel and non-metal minerals from rocks (Ukpong, 2012). According to Chizoro *et al.*, (1997) quarrying has land use policy implications. It is either agriculture contends with quarrying, or a coexistence of both. With agriculture, conflict over traditional uses of land often arises. The authors also added that the clearing of land to develop access roads and open up mining sites destroys habitats for wild animals, reduces grazing, and sources of plant life for human beings and animals.

Besides affecting the locals, the noise from blasting and transport activities has, in some instances, caused migration from surrounding areas, thus affecting ecological balance through the disruption of the food chain (Maponga and Munyanduri, 1998). Stehouwer *et al.* (2006) also posited that quarrying activities exert tremendous pressure on limited soil and water resources, thus increasing the rate of erosion processes and subsequent damage of existing arable lands. Quarrying operations can intensely modify preexisting ecosystems and disturb hydro-geological and hydrological regimes. They can strongly modify the substratum; transform landscape patterns and integrity; destroy natural habitats and disrupt natural succession; as well as change genetic resources. Quarrying of solid mineral through open cast mining techniques without reclamation consequently predisposes terrestrial patterns of ecosystem to becoming aquatic. Castro and Nielsen (2001) explain that, conflicts resulting from natural resource exploitation are typically severe and debilitating, resulting in violence, resource degradation, and the uprooting of communities, and if not addressed, can threaten to unravel the entire fabric of a society. With each party wanting to pursue its own interests to the full, they end up

contradicting, compromising, or even defeating the interest of others (Ochieng-Odhiambo, 2000).

Atmospheric Impacts of Quarrying

The primary source of noise during stone quarrying are earth-moving and processing equipment, as well as blasting (Langer, 2001). Blasting, which occurs at quarries, can give rise to vibration, audible noise, fly rocks and dust. However, the levels of vibration caused by blasting are well below those which can cause structural damage to properties. Nonetheless, vibration transmitted through the ground and pressure waves through the air (air overpressure) can shake buildings and people, and may constitute nuisances. Audible noise accompanies overpressure. Noise can cause annoyance, nuisance, sleep disturbance and can also affect wildlife. Residential properties, schools, hospitals, nursing homes, churches, and others are also noise-sensitive receptors. The impacts of noise are highly dependent on the sound source, the topography, land use, ground cover of the surrounding site, and climatic conditions. The beat, rhythm, pitch of noise, and distance from the noise source affect the impact of the noise on the receiver (Langer, 2001).

Dust is one of the most visible, invasive, and potentially irritating impacts associated with quarrying. Its visibility often raises concerns that are not directly proportional to its impact on human health and the environment (Howard and Cameron, 1998). Dust may occur as fugitive dust from excavation, haul roads, and blasting, or point sources, such as drilling, crushing and screening (Langer, 2001). Dust pollution from quarrying operations affects local air quality. Quarry dust not only pollutes the air, but may also lead to serious health problems. Quarrying generates dust, both on site and on roads. Dust emissions tend to affect animals, vegetation and agriculture, although the precise effects

still need to be more extensively researched (IUCN, 1996). However, incidences of animals inhaling dust containing dangerous (silica) substances have been recorded, as well as oxygen deprivation of plants and trees, which may lead to a plant disease called asphyxia (Akatch, 2004). Therefore, residents living in proximity to quarries, and quarry workers can potentially be affected by dust. The main potential effects of dust are visual impacts; coating/soiling of property (including housing, washing, and cars); coating of vegetation; contamination of soils; water pollution; change in plant species composition; loss of sensitive plant species; increased inputs of mineral nutrients and altered pH balances.

Hydrospheric Impacts of Quarrying

Mining is responsible for changing the hydrology of an area in many ways. Sometimes, mining changes the river course and flow discharge, thereby affecting the agriculture, flora and fauna of the area. Quarrying can substantially modify the routing and water quality (Gunn and Hobbs, 1999). Commonly, the first impact of quarrying is to remove the overlying vegetation and soil. The removal of topsoil, overburden and aggregates may affect the quality of water recharging of an aquifer, and excavation below the water table may lead to de-watering of adjacent watercourses and wells (Gunn and Hobbs, 1999). If the protective soil cover or unsaturated rock is removed, the hole created by the mining may focus surface water to the ground-water system. As a result, the quantity, and physical and chemical quality, of surface waters and ground waters may be affected and flows can be increased or decreased and may be contaminated by runoff or dust from the quarry (Ekmekçi, 1993). Mining of solid minerals without site reclamation consequentially modifies ecosystem patterns from terrestrial to aquatic, thereby introducing alien pathogen into the environment, contrary to the existing ones. Deposits of quarrying tail

into the river water, especially those with pollutants like phosphate which promote eutrophication process. Those with iron and heavy metals influence the less harmful mercury in stagnant water bodies, leading to bioaccumulation and magnification of carcinogenic agents, and shortage of aquatic animals' lifespans.

Biospheric Impacts of Quarrying

Dusts of various primary chemical components released into the atmosphere in the process of prospecting, exploration and development react with other atmospheric gases to form secondary pollutants. Acid rain forms as a result of the reaction of secondary pollutants with water molecules in the atmosphere. Sulphur dioxide (SO_2) and oxidized nitrogen oxides (NO_x) are the primary molecules that coalesce to form acid rain. The effects of acid rain on ecosystems are often subtle and difficult to quantify. In many parts of the world, especially in Central Europe and Northeastern North America, acid rain is suspected of being the cause of the death of many forests, as well as reducing the vigour and rate of growth of others. A strong relationship can be established between the reduction of the vegetation and acid rain. The deposition of acid causes major changes to the soils in areas where the soils are unable to buffer the additional acid. As soil becomes acidic, aluminum is released from binding sites and becomes part of the soil water, where it interferes with the ability of plant roots to absorb nutrients. Soils derived from igneous rock are not capable of buffering the effect of acid deposition, while soils derived from sedimentary rocks such as limestone release bases that neutralize the effects of acids (Enger and Smith, 2009). Many years of acid deposition may reduce the amount of Ca and Mg in the soil, which are essential plant growth requirements. Decline in soil pH may alter the kinds of bacteria in the soil and reduce the nutrient availability for plant development.

The mining and quarrying sector is traditionally a sector that poses large risks to occupational health and safety. Even in modern quarries and mines, fatal injuries occur regularly (CREM, 2005). The most frequent occupational risks related to stone quarrying are fatal accidents such as physical injuries requiring medical treatment. Work-related illnesses endemic to the natural stone industry include respiratory diseases like silicosis and tuberculosis (or silica-tuberculosis). Large numbers of quarry workers suffer from silicosis or tuberculosis due to prolonged inhalation of silica-dust. According to Langer (2001), it is estimated that some 4 million people die each year from acute respiratory problems in developing countries, for the most part being aggravated by environmental pollution emanating from quarrying, sandblasting and emission of dangerous chemicals. Dust particles produced during mining operations are highly injurious to workers' health, primarily causing pneumoconiosis (black lungs).

Financial Impacts of Quarrying

On the other hand, quarrying is characterized by positive economic multiplier effects by supporting livelihood, creating employment, and generating income and revenue. Even though agriculture remains the key strategy for rural poverty reduction, small scale mineral extraction is as well playing a critical role in rural livelihood improvement thereby creating additional job opportunity and helping to generate additional income (Fellmann *et al.*, 2005). According to Wang *et al.* (2010), over 500 million people in developing countries engage in occupations such as small-scale surface mining and quarrying for survival. In Africa, East Asia, Southeast Asia, and Latin America, accessibility to natural resources plays a critical role in the livelihood conditions of people. Since the formal sectors in developing countries have very little potential in terms of job creation (Ibrahim, 2007), the informal

sector has become an attractive alternative for achieving livelihood needs.

A livelihood comprises of capabilities, assets and activities required for living. It is considered sustainable when it can cope with and recover from stress and shocks, maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets, and provide sustainable livelihood opportunities for the next generation; and contributes net benefits to other livelihoods at the local and global levels, and in the short and long duration (Chambers and Conway, 1992). This approach is relevant to stone quarrying in understanding how individuals meet their needs using minimal financial input, simple technology and indigenous resources amidst a competitive formal market and restrictive government policy. Stone workers use the different assets (human, capital, financial, physical, natural and social capital) they have in order to achieve the different livelihood outcomes. In an effort to ensure sustainable development, laws and policies are often in place to limit overexploitation of these resources (Helmore and Singh, 2001)

Quarrying activities generate employment and contribute to a country's gross national product, both through production for the local market and export trade (National Council of Bhutan, 2013). Kuntala (2000) stated that stone quarrying generates considerable employment opportunities as it is a relatively labor intensive, under-mechanized industry, although accurate data on the sector's contribution to overall employment is difficult to establish. For example, in India, around 2 million people were employed in the sand stone mining. Yet, population growth and concomitant high demand for natural resources have put severe stress on the available resources, with dire consequences on their sustainability. Overexploitation of the natural environment has depleted most resources and rendered most productive land beyond repairs (IEG, World Bank, 2008). This development is

likely to compound the health and unemployment problems of the poor majority seeking alternative means of livelihoods in rural areas.

Empirical Studies of Quarrying Impact on Ecosystem Deterioration

The terms 'quarrying' and 'sustainable development' in urban areas appear incompatible. Yet, Kaliampakos and Benardos (2000) examined the two terms side-by-side, using Athens, Greece, as a case study. The existence of quarries near or even within the boundaries of urban centres is the cause for many environmental problems, despite their significant contribution to the cities' development. Hence, the question arises as to how quarrying activities can be compromised within the essence of sustainable development in big cities. In the case of Athens, two dominant, though opposing opinions were formed. The first argued that all quarries must be forced to suspend their activities as soon as possible, whereas the second pressed for the continuation of quarrying. Consequently, the question was transposed on the dilemma between improved environmental conditions and economic development. The authors' work presented a viewpoint demonstrating that if a complete redesign is employed to specific, non-visible quarrying sites, the continuation of quarrying activities is acceptable and a good compromise can be achieved as trade-off between the meeting of economic demand and environmental protection.

Lameed and Ayodele (2010) studied the effect of quarrying activities on biodiversity in Ogbere, an unexploited site in Ogun State, Nigeria. The study employed both direct and indirect line-transect, while the Mueller-Dombois and Ellenberg analysis was adopted for the vegetation. The researchers discovered that the most abundant species are the Rodentia and Viverridae families, while the Artiodactyla and Carnivora are on the verge of extinction, due to prevailing uncondusive

conditions at the site. The study concluded that the forest ecosystem of the unexploited plot of quarry at Ogbere is a seriously disturbed site, due to scanty natural resources that have been impacted by quarry activities.

Ginevra *et al.* (2015) investigated the relationship between quarry activities and municipal spatial planning, with possible mediation, in the case of Sardinia, Italy. The paper investigated the state of natural and recycled aggregates, how to limit the production of natural aggregates and how to increase the use of recycled aggregates in the study area. The result of the research showed how the combined use of natural aggregates and recycled aggregates can help meet the local and regional demand for aggregates. Possible strategies for limiting the consumption of natural aggregates, as well as the use of recycled aggregates, were also described.

Dina and Sefa (2015) examined the roles of the mining industry in corporate social responsibility in Ghana, using evidence from two mining communities. The study considered two major mining companies in Ghana, AngloGold Ashanti and Newmont Ghana Gold Limited. Samples were drawn from the communities in which these companies operate, in order to determine the impact CSR has had on various dimensions of community development. It was discovered that, in Ghana, the debate is not about whether CSR is developmental or not, but rather what strategies and policies can help increase CSR efficiency. Findings also suggested that CSR accounted for several visible infrastructure in mining communities. However, there is a major flaw in not empowering community members and improving their livelihoods.

Afeni and Adeogun (2015) assessed the socio-economic impacts of limestone quarrying and processing operations at Ewekoro, South-Western Nigeria. Data were collected through the use of well-structured pre-tested questionnaires. Oral interviews

were conducted to assess the socio-economic impact of quarrying and processing limestone on the inhabitants of the community and the workers. Findings showed that limestone exploitation has both positive and negative effects on the host community and the workers. It also showed that the benefits derived by the host community like employment, good roads, schools and hospitals are insignificant when compared to the negative effects of the exploitation. Those effects include reduction in crop production, negligence of education by students, overcrowding, and high competition for scarce social amenities. Besides, the socioeconomic inputs of the companies were not well felt by the communities due to politicizing of the executions. Appropriate recommendations were made to ameliorate these negative socioeconomic effects.

Akinsulore (2016) conducted a research on the effects of legislation on corporate social responsibility in the Nigerian mineral and mines sector. He observed that Nigeria's extractive industrial sector is populated by enclave industries which give little priority to corporate social responsibility. He analyzed the Nigerian Minerals and Mines Act, 2007 which obligates contracting a community development agreement (CDA) between the mineral title holder and the host mining community. Linking corporate social responsibility and the CDA, through the stakeholder theory, corporate actors in the country's solid minerals sector can no longer deprioritize corporate social responsibility in their corporate planning. He concluded that the effect of this law is to empower the community as an important stakeholder, thereby validating the stakeholder thesis therein espoused.

Oyinloye and Ajayi (2016) researched on environmental impact of quarry activities in Oba-Ile, Ondo State, Nigeria. Structured questionnaires and field observation were used to elucidate data on socio-economic characteristics of the residents; vibration effects; building damages; health effects; and

impact of quarry activities on the environment, among others. Results showed that most buildings within the buffer zone of the quarry site are prone to high risks such as air and noise pollution and health challenges. The study recommended total relocation for the residents in the study area, in order to avoid attendant health risks.

In 2016, Tahseen studied the environmental impact assessment of quarries and stone cutting industries in Palestine. He observed that the particulate matter (dust) produced as a result of the different activities associated with these industries causes several problems to the environment and residents. Measurements of air quality showed high concentrations of different particulate matter in the study area. Majority of the people (70% of the respondents) confirmed that air is permanently dusty, and the condition is not limited to working hours. Higher effects are normally noticed in summer. Also, the study showed that these industries have negative impact on water resources, and about 68% of the respondents confirmed that the groundwater is polluted as a result of the industrial wastes. Furthermore, the study demonstrated high prevalence of diseases, particularly air pollution leading to cough and cold, dyspnea, nasal inflammation, and asthma, as well as hearing impairment due to noise pollution. Moreover, these industries cause stress and discomfort to people and affect their homes as different degrees of crack are developed due to vibrations.

Zelalem (2016) assessed the environmental and socioeconomic impacts of quarrying in peri-urban areas of Addis Ababa. He explored the livelihood outcomes realized from stone quarrying activities by the stone workers and local community. The study was a descriptive research, which collected the required information through structured and unstructured questionnaires and field observations. The findings showed that the quarrying activities in the study area aid the

development of other informal business activities such as petty trading, house renting and small scale transport service provision which support the local community. They serve as alternative means of livelihood and transform them from rural to urban activities. Regarding the environment, the bulk excavation pits, overburden wastes, together with poor management of quarries resulted in land use cover and landscape changes as well as land degradation and water resource depletion.

To evaluate the effect of mining in Nigeria, Ali *et al.* (2018) studying the environmental issues and prospects of mining concluded that the activity is characteristically destructive on environmental components, such as air and water quality, alongside destruction of land and habitats, leading to biodiversity loss. It also takes a toll on the health of people living around mines.

In addition, majority of the time, agitation for community rights results in conflicts between host communities and mining companies. This is owing to habitual deviation from the implementation of CSR and the EIA. Conflicts between parties occasionally result in vandalization, and loss of life and properties in the concerned community. Also, the affected communities are unable to bail themselves out of the predicaments that the mining industry have subjected them to, due to poor government policies.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Mining, irrespective of location (rural or urban) poses irreparable harm to the biophysical environment, which dims in comparison to the compensations and benefits contained in signed EIAs. Mining activities in Nigeria operate below capacity, in the absence of the enforcement of laid-down regulations and standards. Yet, mining activities can have positive impact on the environment and host

communities, if sustainable and modern methods are adopted. Recycling, improving legislation and regulations, proper environmental management systems, proper mines closure and site reclamation processes should be adopted as strategies to combat the negative effects of mining activities in the country.

To ameliorate the adverse consequences of mining on the biophysical environment, environmental management principles need to be incorporated into the EIA programme. It becomes imperative to enforce land reclamation, particularly where open cast mining is preponderant, to avoid the development of alien ecosystems that may predispose communities to health challenges arising therefrom. Strategic land-filling of the opened earth, especially where quarries have been operated, will go a long way in gradually returning the environment to its former ecological state.

Creation of buffer zones with the integration of rapid growing trees around the mining area, to sieve and reduce the radially dispersed dust beyond the operation zone can also improve the environment. This study further suggests that rather than providing social amenities for the affected community, CSR should extend to restoration of the deformed biophysical environment. Introduction of polluters-pay-principle (PPP) is highly encouraged. Strict adherence to the deed of ESIA could also forestall community-industry conflicts while administrative head offices of mining industries must be forced to be situated within the mining operation environment.

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